

FORMATION AND PROBLEMS IN THE CATERING SYSTEM IN UZBEKISTAN (DURING THE SOVIET PERIOD)

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СТАНОВЛЕНИЕ И ПРОБЛЕМЫ СИСТЕМЫ ОБЩЕСТВЕННОГО ПИТАНИЯ В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ (В СОВЕТСКИЙ ПЕРИОД)

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O'ZBEKISTONDA OVQATLANISH TIZIMINING SHAKLLANISHI VA MUAMMOLARI (SOVET DAVRIDA)

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abstract

In the article totalitarian Soviet regime, the process of the formation of public service system, the system of government programs in this area plans and the implementation of these plans in the conflict regions the main problems in the system and information in the case of career in the Soviet republics were analyzed on the basis of the scientific literature, periodicals and archival documents.

аннотация

В статье тоталитарный советский режим, процесс формирования системы государственной службы, система государственных программ в этой области, планы и реализация этих планов в конфликтных регионах, основные проблемы в системе и информации в случае карьеры в советских республиках были проанализированы на основе научная литература, периодические издания и архивные документы.

annotatsiya

Maqolada totalitar sovet rejimi, davlat xizmatlari tizimini shakllantirish jarayoni, ushbu sohadagi

davlat dasturlari tizimi rejalari va ushbu rejalarni ziddiyatli hududlarda amalga oshirish sovet respublikalarida martaba holatida tizim va ma'lumotlarning asosiy muammolari tahlil qilindi. ilmiy adabiyotlar, davriy nashrlar va arxiv hujjatlari.

Keywords:

public service system, "socialist" way of life, handicrafts, programs, Union Soviet republics, plan, industry, indexes, researchers, and cadre

Ключевые слова:

система государственной службы, "социалистический" образ жизни, ремесла, программы, Союзные советские республики, план, промышленность, показатели, исследователи и кадры.

Kalit so'zlar:

davlat xizmati tizimi, "sotsialistik" hayot tarzi, hunarmandchilik, dasturlar, ittifoq sovet respublikalari, reja, sanoat, indekslar, tadqiqotchilar va kadrlar.

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Introduction

Today, the history of our reporting is one of the priority tasks facing our society, which is one of the main driving force of the development of the historical society.

Studying the history of Uzbekistan, in particular, to eliminate the problems in the daily life of the population living in the Soviet Union was an important role in the history of the public service system as a whole.

Public service system is a comprehensive system, if the system is put to the right way it will be a special place in people's daily lives. It also is important to note that the level of the daily life of the population has the integral character, we can get adequate information through political, socio-economic and cultural level of a particular state. [1]

As we know, a number of programs and development plans were processed concerning to the idea of creating "socialist" life or build a "socialist city" [2.-P.4] in the country of the Soviet. One of the main ideas of creating in a way "Socialist" life in the country that is planned to improve the living and working conditions of the population. To this end, attention was paid to raise the living standards of the population. Especially, the public service system influenced to the economic, political and cultural sectors of the life in a socialist society [3.-P.3].

Research results

In fact, there were skilled artisans, carpenters, blacksmiths, and a variety of service areas schools in the ancient times of Uzbekistan, which were created as a result of the people to overcome many of the problems of daily life.

Materials which were created by craftsmen assessed in the World Exhibition in Paris in 1867, Russia, Moscow in 1873-1876 years of professional and technical exhibition, in 1895 and 1904 America's top international exhibitions in the cities of Atlanta and San Louis. In 1870 the Queen of Russia came to Turkestan, during a visit to an exhibition of handicrafts by Uzbek artisans, recognized for their beauty and elegance, so it has been documented a long day shopping [4.-P. 6].

When Central Asia was joined by Russia, such as a variety of products for the production of large enterprises were built in Tashkent, Samarkand, and Kokand city. As a result of this, negative impact on the activities of the local handicraft. General products with the products of factories and plants in general became more indebted private ownership of competitors and led to less demand for their products on the market [5-B 48-49].

20 years of the twentieth century, the public service sector was tried to create a socialist direction by the Soviet government. For this purpose, the public service artels were created, and some new ateliers, workshops, service homes, businesses were opened. The large enterprises which estimated to produce a variety of products were built. This, in turn adversely affected the work of craftsmanship. As a result, the service industry was founded in the country.

At the same time, the Soviet government started to carry out not to care the national interests of the country's population, Uzbekistan's specialization in the supply of raw materials [6.-P.11].

In 1921, the "Turkistan Handicrafts Union (Turkpromsoyuz)" was founded [7.-P.16]. The craftsmen in the country began the process of cooperation, public service providers in a number of areas of state-controlled industrial enterprises has already started. For example, in 1921 in Tashkent 50 Barbers' specialized artels began to work [8.-P.7].

In 1924, after the completion of the Turkestan Handicraft fair, the first Handicraft department in "Uzbekselkredpromsoyuz" organization was founded. Later this division was changed into the Bureau of Uzbekistan Handicraft cooperation. However, these agencies weren't operated in the long term [9.-P.70].

In October 1925, Uzbekistan Handicrafts Union (Uzpromsoyuz) was founded [10.-P.70]. In 1925, there were 251 combined artels with 6,581 members in this union [11.-P.38-41]. "Handicrafts Union" in all its activities included areas such as agricultural materials, cultural and community services, leather and felt footwear work, textile-sewing and knitting-related services, waste-raw materials processing, transport, metal and wood processing, and the sale of handicraft products [12.-P.1-2].

Uzbek SSR was established, in accordance with the public service carried out by 3 systems - Uzbek Crafts Cooperation Council, the Local industrial Public Commissioner and the Council of People with Disabilities Commissioner [13.-P. 6-7]. The country's city councils organized daily sections at Working under the Presidium of the Central Executive Committee, Soviet Women's Committee of improving the lives of farmers and labor [14.-B.7-8], they determined in their work to learn the status of the population living in cities, open clubs to improve the living condition of households, in particular, to organize the opening of the common kitchen areas. It should be noted that a special kind of public catering establishments were required to come to open the faces of the women in the local community [15.-P.19-20].

In 1926 at a permanent Commission which was created in order to improve the everyday lives of women of the Uzbek Soviet Central Executive Committee did significant work in determining the amount of women service and working with them,

creating weavers' and laundress' team and in establishing the production of cotton quilts [16.-P.19-20]. Archive documents indicated at the end of the 20th century, shoemakers and craftsmen compared to the situation in the neighboring republics of Uzbekistan for a decline [17.-P.74], to ensure the required qualified personnel was the unsatisfactory situation of the republic, it was said about sending unworthy specialists and specialists who didn't know the Uzbek languages [18.-P.75-76].

During this period, public service institutions were under various organizations. In particular, on the base of the decree of the Soviet government in May 1931 "About consumer cooperatives" hairdressers' and tailors' workshops which were in consumer cooperatives joined to Handicrafts cooperative, laundry posts joined to the City Council [19.-P.301-305]. In recent years, the name of the management of the system has been changed. For example, It was renamed in 1932 under the " Uzbekistan Handicrafts Council", in 1934 " Uzbekistan Handicrafts Union" and in 1938 "Uzbekistan Arts Council" [20.-P.17], in 1944 the Council of People's Commissars Handicraft Cooperation Department, in 1950 Handicraft fair the Board of Directors Cooperation Department [21.-P.1]. In 1960 Uzbekistan Handicraft Cooperation Department was liquidated [22.-P.1]. In 1962, the General Directorate of Local Industry of Uzbekistan was renamed into the department of public services of Uzbekistan [23.-P.23]. Only in the year 1966, the activities of the public service system began to work as a separate ministry of the Republic [24.-P.118].

During the first years of the 1960s, public service work carried out by the various ministries and agencies of the country's department of the local industry, "O'zbekbirlashuv", the Ministry of Commerce, 14 utilities, such as the Ministry of Agriculture and Ministry of Communications [25.-P.21], the same period in 1970, the utility of the Ministry of Agriculture, the Ministry of Health, the Ministry of light industry, the Ministry of Commerce, the Ministry of Agriculture, the Ministry of Oil processing industry, "DOSAAF", the National Committee, in short totally 14 top management of public service [26.-P.20]. In this regard, the results of research by the 1970s, half of the amount of public service ministries and agencies reached 17 [27.-P.10].

According to the observations the public service work was carried out by various agencies, created a series of negative events. That is, the same direction of service facilities in some districts were located close to each other, in other districts in the direction of this type of service weren't organized [28.-P.10].

Based on the decisions of the XXIII Congress of the Communist Party, in the Soviet Union to develop significantly public service providers, to change this system into a highly mechanized sector of the economy [29.-P.15-16], to raise the living

standards of the people, especially to make closer social economic and cultural living standards among the population of the city and village were planned [30.-P.135].

In this regard, a number of plans were identified in the Republic. In particular, in 1966 on the measure "About improvement of public service in Uzbekistan" by the decision of Central Committee of Uzbekistan Communist party and the Council of Ministers, such issues reflected in plans: to increase the volume of consumer services, to use achievements in the sphere of science and technology, to build large-scale specialized-mechanized enterprises and the establishment of institutions and to provide them with mature and skilled personnel, to improve public service and develop the system of socialist competition, to build public service new facilities in rural areas and to improve the quality of work, to reduce the period of execution, to improve service culture, to introduce new forms and types of consumer services, to execute orders ahead of schedule and quality of service, to improve public service culture, to introduce new types of service system and to end the year 1966 with positive outcomes [31.-P.58].

In order to know the opinion of the population, on the activities of the system, on November 1966, the Ministry of Uzbekistan Public General service and the administration of the newspaper "Pravda Vostoka" (Trust of the East) printed the survey questionnaires under the heading "What were you being serviced?". This questionnaire was determined how the system was organized and how the representatives work was. For example: the quality of the work performed by the service sector of the population was estimated at 25%, some of the officials for their negligence (unfair) approached 20%, the low level of qualification of agents was 15%, services 10% of the afflicted, the rude behavior of service providers 8% of the work in public service institutions assessed as satisfactory by 22% [32.-P.176-177].

As we see from the example of the work of the system, 115 collective and state farms did not exist as permanent public service institutions in the country in 1966. It was analyzed that only 1-2 directions of daily service offices among 10 collective farms and wasn't organized any daily service offices on 2 collective farms in Andijan region. In the Bukhara region, 19 collective farms of agricultural service establishments weren't organized only 1-2 line service workshops on 65 collective farms. There weren't any service workshops on 6 collective farms of the Samarkand region and, only 1-2 line service workshops of public services set up on 53 collective farms [33.-P.63-67].

In spite of the labor resources in excess of 200 thousand people in the city of Tashkent, nearly 125 workers and staff attracted to the republic. In the first place their organizations have been provided with the housing and other conditions, which was

the most important problem for local population. [34.-P.106]. Especially large population migrations were observed from Russia, the Ukraine, and Kazakhstan. [35.-P. 114].

In fact, of all the economic and social indicators were significantly behind the average of the Former Soviet Union, which was one of the last places in the country. Per capita gross social product for the 12 place, the per capita national income was double in the Soviet Union, average level of production was low, that was in 1971-1987 years in Soviet state 175 percent, but in Uzbekistan was 139 percent [36.-P. 16]. Summing up, the conditions of dependence and tyranny have become an integral part of people's lifestyles institutions to significantly slow the development of public services, as well. In the process, two different trends in the consumer services sector of the population lives going into the barrier. First, of course, our dependence conditions, the national mentality and way of life, and did not accept the ideology of forcible imposition of other cultures. Because the purpose of the introduction of public service facilities during the Soviet "socialist lifestyle" to complete the introduction. Second, the changes made to the system of the public service needs of the population and the local uniqueness of origin, and most importantly, the formation of the infrastructure of the industry and training a blind eye to the problems associated with them. As a result, the welfare of the country among the Soviet republics fell to its lowest level in many indicators of development institutions. Thus, the envisaged public service institutions remained very sad and controversial case.

Conclusion

Above based information there observed the following conclusions:

- The authorities in the Soviet rule was established, not only in politically dependent on the country, but also in economic, cultural and began to affect the way of living;

- It is difficult to imagine the daily life of the population absence of public service systems. That is why the leadership of the communist party people will be affected by such a system, which "socialist" to spread among the population in a way that drew attention to the level of state policy;

- The creation of decent conditions, to improve the social system, this time on the development of the system of public service shortcomings identified by the researchers are not given sufficient attention by the government;

- To serve the people, to promote traditional practices contrary to the national traditions;

- Soviet republics to improve the public service delivery system and the amount of the birth of the features of the development of the demographic features of the

national traditions of the rural population, climatic conditions, as well as higher incomes and serious attention for other reasons.

This attitude in this area is covered in scientific works [37.].

These conditions give the totalitarian Soviet regime, the system of public service in the conflict and of the representatives of the industry to the development of the demand will be high. The reason for the shortcomings of their own plans for the future in this area thoroughly explored and considered a number of plans and measures. Most importantly, the activities of the public service system of the Soviet Union were one of the last places.

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